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The Concept and Duties of Prosecutorial Supervision over the Implementation of Human Rights and Freedoms Laws

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Abstract: *as a result of the reforms carried out in the last years of this scientific article, the legislative guarantees of the rights of participants in the criminal process have significantly expanded. It is worth saying that the criminal interpretation will always be associated with limiting the rights and freedoms of people and citizens, as well as the rights of participants involved in the criminal process. These rights include: listening to telephone conversations; catching; searching; browsing and other rights.*

Key words: *rights, freedoms, society, Justice, lawyer, suspect, defendant.*

In addition to protecting the rights of the suspect, the accused (using the help of a lawyer from the moment of arrest, not testifying against himself and his loved ones, the right to silence, not allowing the use of evidence obtained in violation of the law in a fair trial), hattoki was guaranteed to protect the rights of persons affected by the crime (protection,.¹ The main stage in the development of guarantees of rights and freedoms of participants in the criminal proceedings is associated with the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the new edition.

The real reason is that, in accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a person, his rights and freedoms are considered a high value, and this, in turn, is the responsibility of the state, where the recognition, observance and protection of the rights and freedoms of a person and a citizen is represented by special competent bodies. Under Section 29 (4) of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the rule of not allowing the use of evidence obtained in violation of the law in justice is directed directly to the Inquirer, investigator, prosecutor and court. Compliance with the legality and validity of restrictions on these rights control is an integral part of the responsibility of the prosecutor's office. Because, the inquiry, the limitation of rights in the process of preliminary investigation is

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Конституцияси. – Т.: Ўзбекистон, 2023.

associated with the criminal prosecution of the suspect and the accused. However, when talking about the limitation of the rights of the suspect, the accused, the witness involved in the criminal process, especially the victim, should not be forgotten about their rights and freedoms. Despite the undoubtedly positive changes in the judicial sphere, almost every fourth crime remains unopened, so the situation with the degree of exposure of the crime should not be considered normal. Illegal and unreasonable refusal to initiate criminal cases, suspension and termination of criminal cases negatively affect the implementation of the tasks of quick and complete opening of crimes.

For example, in 6 months of 2024, the decision to refuse was canceled, and the number of crimes committed falls on 2827. In 6 2024, the number of crimes hidden from account by employees of the internal affairs body is 32. The survey is talking about the dynamics of deterioration of the data presented on the state of legality at the initial stage of Investigation. On the one hand, the survey can see how the information about the cancellation of illegal procedural decisions of the preliminary investigative bodies by prosecutors makes an important contribution to the detection and elimination of cases of violations of the law in the pre-trial stages of a criminal case. On the other hand, issues such as non-registration of criminal petitions and arrests by the harassment Authority, non-prosecution, termination of criminal proceedings lead to a gross violation of the constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens affected by the crime to achieve justice and compensation for the damage done to them. The state has distributed the relevant function to all state entities of Criminal Procedural activity and to those entities carrying criminal prosecution. The prosecutor is an official who carries out criminal prosecution on behalf of the state in criminal proceedings, as well as supervision over the procedural activities of the pre-investigation examination, inquiry and preliminary investigative bodies. It turns out that the inquiry, strengthening the legitimacy of the preliminary investigation, while at the same time increasing the role of the prosecutor's control in the performance of the duties of the criminal process. The main reason for this is the specialized system of prosecutorial supervision, a centralized body.

Especially in the field of ensuring the rights and freedoms of a person and a citizen, there are a lot of opinions on the issues of setting the tasks and goals of the prosecutor's control. "The duties of the prosecutor's supervision include: the implementation of prosecutorial supervision, the fight against crime, the enforcement of laws, the provision of the rule of law, the protection of citizens' rights, the prevention and Prevention of violations, the Coordination of law enforcement activities, the fight against violations, the implementation of measures to eliminate violations in a timely manner."²

V.M. Saviskiy it is noted that "in the control of the implementation of laws, the prosecutor's office operates in strictly regulated forms".³

V. Karimov in his opinion, "the goals and objectives of the prosecutor's control are determined in accordance with criminal procedural legislation".⁴

K.F. Skvorsov, "the hierarchical system of defined goals distinguishes btshyicha into five levels: 1) to take measures to eliminate violations, restore violated rights, prevent possible circumstances; 2) to practically eliminate violations and restore rights, punish those responsible, eliminate violations; 3) to

² Ўзбекистон Республикаси 2001 йил 29 августдаги 257-II-сон «Прокуратура тўғрисида»ги Қонуни.

³ Савицкий В. М. Очерк теории прокурорского надзора в уголовном судопроизводстве. М., 1975.

⁴ Каримов Ваҳобжон. Тезкор-кидирув фаолияти: дарслик / В.Каримов – Тошкент, Lesson press, 2021. – 410 - б.

prevent violations of laws; 4) to protect the rights and legitimate interests of officials and citizens from any violations; 5) to strengthen the rule of law".⁵

B.X. Po'latov, "the inquiry divided the objectives of the prosecutor's control over the enforcement of laws by the bodies of preliminary investigation into the following types: (a) that no crime remains unmasked and that not every person who commits a crime gets rid of the responsibility established by law; that the capture of a citizen suspected of committing a crime is carried out according; b) compliance with the rules in the process of investigating crimes, requiring all cases in the case to be considered comprehensively, thoroughly and objectively, to identify situations that both expose and justify the defendant, as well as both alleviate and aggravate his liability; v) the procedure for initiating and investigating a criminal case established by law, compliance with the terms of Investigation, ; no one is allowed to be criminally liable without law and grounds, or to limit other rights without law; g) no one shall be arrested or held in custody based on a court order; the reasons for the crime and the conditions that allowed them to take place, as well as measures aimed at their elimination, shall be determined".⁶

"The survey, the main task of the prosecutor's control over the enforcement of laws by the bodies of preliminary investigation: to ensure the rule of law, strengthen legality, protect the rights and freedoms of citizens, the law-guarded interests of society and the state, protect the Constitutional Order of the Republic of Uzbekistan, prevent and prevent violations".⁷

Now, briefly covering the above-mentioned duties of the prosecutor, it occupies an important place in the activities of the prosecutor's office in the Prevention of violations of the law in the field of delimiting the rights and legitimate interests of citizens provided for by the Constitution and legislation. Here, " the word prevention is not seen as a task, but as one of the elements of the concept of "conservation""..⁸

The prosecutor's office provides for the protection of the interests of society and the state, the constitutional order, ensuring the rights of individuals and citizens, the rule of law, the control of the prosecutor over the clear implementation of laws and the identification of cases of violations of laws, taking measures to eliminate violations, generalizing the facts of violations, studying their causes and conditions The principle of unity of prosecutorial control in criminal proceedings is that at all stages of the proceedings, the essence of prosecutorial control remains unchanged, that is, at any stage, the same tasks stand before the prosecutorial supervision, making the same requirements as control over the exact and uniform implementation of laws. In our national legislation, the direct tasks of prosecutorial supervision are to strengthen the rule of law, protect the rights and freedoms of a person and a citizen. According to Article 143 of the Constitution of the Republic, "control over the clear and uniform implementation of laws on the territory of the country is entrusted to the prosecutor of the Republic and its subordinate prosecutors".⁹

Control over the implementation of laws has set itself the goal of strengthening the rule of law in our country, protecting the interests of society and the state, protecting individuals and legal entities from

⁵ Скворцов К.Ф. Проблемы эффективности прокурорского надзора. - М.: Юрид. лит.- 1977.-С. 10-11.

⁶ Пулатов Б.Х., Набиев О.Х., Бабажанов Б.Б. Суриштирув ва дастлабки тергов органларида қонунлар ижроси устидан прокурор назорати. Илмий-амалий қўлланма. – Тошкент: Азия-пресс, 2015. 11-бет.

⁷ Пулатов Б.Х., Набиев О.Х., Бабажанов Б.Б. Суриштирув ва дастлабки тергов органларида қонунлар ижроси устидан прокурор назорати. Илмий-амалий қўлланма. – Тошкент: Азия-пресс, 2015. 12-бет.

⁸ Качурин Д.В, Криминология. Учебное пособие. - Тверь: Твер, гос. Ун-т, 2002.-С.61-63.

⁹ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Конституцияси. – Т.: Ўзбекистон, 2023.

any encroachments on the property and non-property interests guarded by law. It also takes the necessary measures to respect and comply with the rights and freedoms of a person and a citizen during the pre-investigation examination, inquiry, preliminary investigation. In the process of maintaining control over the correct and uniform application of laws in all directions of control during the course of the prosecutor's office, it will be obliged to take measures to eliminate them in a timely manner, regardless of who committed a violation of the law. In accordance with Article 28 of the law "on prosecution", it is one of the main tasks of prosecutors to supervise operational-search activities, inquiry, the exact and uniform implementation of laws by the bodies conducting the preliminary investigation. Consequently, while the prosecutor exercises control over the investigation of criminal cases, he performs both tasks arising from the general function of controlling legality and those that are inherent only in this branch of the prosecutor's control. The peculiarity of the control of the prosecutor's control at the stage of inquiry and preliminary investigation is that, firstly, it carries out supervision over the exact and uniform implementation of laws by the inquiry, preliminary investigative bodies, and, secondly, protects the rights and legitimate interests of persons involved in criminal proceedings (suspect, accused, witness, victim). The prosecutor is obliged to open crimes and find persons who committed crimes, take measures to bring them to justice, protect the interests of persons illegally involved in criminal proceedings, and take measures to obtain a violation by state bodies conducting criminal proceedings. A great deal of responsibility is placed on the prosecutor in the first place about the quick, comprehensive and complete disclosure of each crime. When a crime is exposed as a result of investigative activities prior to the investigation, it takes steps to quickly investigate and initiate an investigation. So, the prosecutor's supervision is tasked with conducting supervision from the moment the criminal application is received until the criminal is read a court verdict. Also, the full disclosure of the crime indicates that the disclosure of all persons who committed a crime in the case, all criminal acts and the reasons and conditions that caused their commission have been determined.

At the same time, it is known to everyone that in some cases, due to the fact that certain shortcomings are allowed in the activities of the investigative and preliminary investigative bodies, crimes remain unrepentant. Among the main reasons for the non-disclosure of crimes may be: improper Organization of operational-search activities, inquiry and investigation, and prosecutorial supervision, insufficient professional skills of investigators, prosecutors and investigators. Therefore, the prosecutor is obliged to coordinate the investigation, the activities of monitoring the enforcement of laws by the authorities that carry out the preliminary investigation. The role of the prosecutor in the gal is to conduct a quick - search in the process of investigating crimes, pre-investigation examination to review complaints made about the actions (inaction) of officials of the body, the interrogator and the investigator. According to Article 55 of the Constitution of the Republic, there are provisions in which everyone has the right to appeal against illegal decisions, actions and inaction of officials. The complaint (application) must be considered in the manner and time limits established by the legislation. These requirements apply fully to the prosecutor's office, including the criminal investigation, the consideration of complaints related to the preliminary investigation. In accordance with Article 7 of the law "on the prosecutor's office", the prosecutor is required to consider complaints about the actions (inaction) of the inquiry and preliminary investigation bodies within the deadlines established by the law and to give written notice to applicants about the decisions made on them. The procedure for dealing with such complaints is also regulated by Articles 27, 338, 358 of the Criminal Procedure Code. By law, proress participants can make written or oral complaints about the illegal act (inaction) and decisions of the interrogator, investigator. The applicant may submit the complaint to the prosecutor directly overseeing the investigation. If the complaint is made orally, a statement is drawn up by the person who received the

complaint and signed by the complainant. Within the period established by the law, the complaint is considered by the prosecutor, who reports its result to the applicant, the complainant. In case of refusal to satisfy the complaint, the prosecutor is obliged to give a justified answer. This procedure increases the responsibility of the prosecutor to properly resolve the complaint. The applicant has the option to appeal the decision of the prosecutor to the superior prosecutor or to the court, knowing the reasons for the dismissal of his appeal (Articles 7, 25, 32 of the law “on the prosecutor's Office”).

Thus, the main purpose of prosecutor's control is to control the exact and uniform implementation and application of laws on the territory of Uzbekistan; the goals of prosecutorial supervision are the final result of the activities of the prosecution authorities aimed at ensuring legitimacy in the country and strengthening the rule of law, protecting the rights and interests of the individual, society and the state; The main task of the prosecutor's control on the net can be distinguished: 1) to protect the constitutional order; 2) to ensure and protect the rights and freedoms of individuals and legal entities; 3) to protect the interests of society and the State; 4) to restore violated rights and to bring the guilty to justice, as well as to The rights and obligations of the prosecutor's office are enshrined and guaranteed in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan (chapter XXV), criminal and Criminal Procedural Law (Article 34) and the law “on the prosecutor's Office”. The rights and obligations enshrined and guaranteed in the laws are important for the prosecutor's office, that is, these rights granted to the prosecutor's office are not just a legal possibility, but it is, on the contrary, an obligation (before the person, society and the state). At the same time, these are not only mandatory requirements, but also the right of the prosecutor's office to implement them. This feature of the prosecutor's office is determined by the peculiarities of their goal, which is aimed at ensuring the rule of uniform law in the state.

In accordance with the law of the prosecutor's office, prosecutors have the following rights: the prosecutor is obliged to check the fulfillment of the requirements of the law on the acceptance, recording and resolution of applications and messages for crimes committed or being prepared at least once a month (Part 3 of Article 28 of the law); by exercising control over the legality, the prosecutor can participate in the preliminary investigation. This is expressed in the formation of an investigative plan, participation in interrogation, examination of the scene, the formation of an operational-search team, holding meetings on the progress of the investigation of crimes (Part 7 of Article 28 of the law); the prosecutor monitors compliance with the conditions of the preliminary investigation; the preliminary investigation must be completed no more than 3 months from the date of the criminal case, until the case is sent to the prosecutor with the indictment, or until the proceedings are terminated or suspended. quick-search, pre-investigation examination will overturn unlawful and unreasonable decisions of an official of the body, as well as interrogators and investigators (Section 28 (4) of the law; agrees to the decision of the Inquirer, investigator to initiate or dismiss a criminal case; pre-investigation examination, operational-search activities, inquiry, investigation will consider the complaint that has fallen on the actions, inaction and decisions of officials of the bodies; criminal prosecution is the responsibility of the prosecutor's function (Article 86 of the CPC) and has other rights and obligations.

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